

**DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF THE LEUKO-GLYCEMIC INDEX
IN CORONARY SLOW FLOW****Oğuz Kılıç¹, Hasan Yıldırım², Derya Kaya³, Ipek Buber³**¹Department of Cardiology, Karaman Training and Research Hospital, Karaman, Turkey²Department of Mathematics, Karamanoglu Mehmet Bey University, Karaman, Turkey³Department of Cardiology, Pamukkale University Hospitals, Denizli, Turkey**ABSTRACT**

The leuko-glycemic index (LGI) is an easy-to-calculate and non-invasive index that combines leukocyte count and blood glucose score. Many studies have shown that LGI is a good clinical predictor of atherosclerotic vascular disease⁸. In this study, we aimed to investigate the usability of LGI in determining Coronary Slow Flow (CSF).

This study was a retrospective and observational study. The clinical, demographic and laboratory data of the patients were obtained from the hospital database. A total of 163 patients with 90 slow coronary flow and 73 normal coronary flow were included in the study. LGI was calculated as mg/dl.mm^3 by multiplying both values and dividing by a thousand¹². Coronary flow rates were calculated using the TIMI frame count (TFC) method¹³.

What stands out in all results, the overall logistic regression model was statistically significant ($\chi^2_{11}=81.3, p<0.001$). The model explained 52.6% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in CSF group and correctly classified approximately 80% of cases. The sensitivity value was calculated as 82.2%, specificity was 76.7% and area under roc curve was 86.9% (AUC: 0.869). LGI score is an effective factor on determination of the existence of CSF with a high odds ratio (**odds = 4.22; [1.14, 15.62] CI 95%**).

A high LGI was a predictor of CSF patients and was found to correlate with the TFC. The use of this simple and inexpensive index, together with other non-invasive tests before CAG, may provide some knowledge about the CSF.

Keywords: Coronary Slow Flow, Leukocyte, Glucose, Angiography

INTRODUCTION

Coronary slow flow (CSF) is characterized by the slow progression of opaque material applied during coronary angiography into the distal vascular structures without occlusion of the epicardial coronary arteries¹. The pathophysiology and clinical significance of CSF have not been fully elucidated. Tambe et al. firstly defined this phenomenon in 1972 and suggested that it may be due to abnormalities in coronary microcirculation². Thrombolysis in myocardial infarction frame count (TFC) was used in the diagnosis of CSF and had been found to be associated with insulin resistance in patients with CSF³.

Hyperglycemia may cause thrombosis and fibrinolysis, which lead to microvascular resistance⁴. Similarly, inflammation is known to trigger endothelial dysfunction and atherosclerotic process⁵. This is evidenced by the demonstration of increased leukocyte levels in many studies. Therefore, leukocyte levels are used as an important indicator in evaluating the risk of cardiovascular disease^{6,7}. The leuko-glycemic index (LGI) is an easy-to-calculate and non-invasive index that combines leukocyte count and blood glucose score. Many studies have shown that LGI is a good clinical predictor of atherosclerotic vascular disease⁸. In this study, we aimed to investigate the usability of LGI in determining CSF.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study populations

This study was a retrospective and observational study. Our study was prepared in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the local ethics committee.

We collected data from the hospital registry system and patients who admitted cardiology clinic due to chest pain and dyspnea in this year were screened and their Coronary angiography (CAG) images were analyzed. A total of 163 patients with 90 slow coronary flow and 73 normal coronary flow were included in the study. Chronic inflammatory disease, obstructive coronary artery disease ($\geq 50\%$ stenosis in the left main coronary artery or $\geq 70\%$ in at least one of the epicardial arteries), cerebrovascular events, coronary artery bypass grafting, valvular heart disease, missing data, cardiogenic shock, previously diagnosed with coronary artery disease (CAD), thyroid disorders, hemolytic disease, malignancy, chronic lung diseases, liver diseases, rheumatic disease, chronic kidney failure and history of hemodialysis and non-regulated diabetes mellitus were excluded. The blood samples at the admission were assessed. The patients were evaluated with the Affiniti 50 echocardiography device before CAG. The left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) was calculated using the modified Simpson method. A resting blood pressure $\geq 140/90$ mmHg in ≥ 2 measurements or taking antihypertensive medication were considered hypertensive (HT)⁹. Patients with fasting blood glucose ≥ 126 mg/dl or postprandial blood glucose ≥ 200 mg/dl or glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) ≥ 6.5 or taking anti-diabetic drugs were considered as diabetes mellitus (DM)¹⁰. A low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) level below the European So-

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676559

ciety of Cardiology Guideline threshold or patients who received an anti-lipidemic were considered to have dyslipidemia¹¹.

Calculation of Leuko-Glycemic Index

Laboratory values of each patient were checked before CAG. Blood glucose was expressed as mg/dl and white blood cell count as the number of cells per mm³. LGI was calculated as mg/dl.mm³ by multiplying both values and dividing by a thousand¹².

Coronary angiography and thrombolysis in the myocardial infarction frame count calculation

Coronary Angiography was performed via the femoral or radial artery, depending on the operator's experience. A routine Judkins catheter was used in the diagnostic CAG. The left main coronary artery (LMCA), left anterior descending (LAD) and left circumflex artery (LCX) were evaluated from the right and left oblique positions using cranial and caudal angles at a rate of 25 fps. Coronary flow rates were calculated using the TIMI frame count (TFC) method¹³.

For TFC measurement, the start and end points were determined separately for LAD, LCX and RCA. The starting point was accepted as the point where the contrast material contacted both sides of the coronary artery and started to progress. Endpoint for LAD, mustache region; The endpoint for RCA was the point at which the first lateral branch was stained with contrast in the posterior lateral artery; For LCX, it is the point where the distal bifurcation of the long branch is visualized. Since LAD lasts longer, the measured value was standardized by dividing it by 1.7. The mean TFC for each participant was calculated by dividing the sum of the TFCs of LAD (corrected), LCX, and RCA by 3. All participants with a corrected TFC greater than 27 (two standard deviations from the published normal range) in at least one of the three epicardial coronary arteries were accepted as having CSF. Those whose TFC fell within the standard deviation of the published normal range were considered as having normal coronary flow.

Statistical analyses

In this study, various statistical methods were applied in order to diagnose the CSF and to determine the factors affecting it. Firstly, the distribution and percentages of qualitative variables on each group are obtained and given in Table 1. The assumptions including the normality, the homogeneity of variance and the linearity required by the tests were checked before applying the statistical analysis. The normality assumption was checked via Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and skewness / kurtosis values with their z-scores, the homogeneity of variance via Levene test and the linearity assumption via scatter plot. Additionally, the possible outliers were observed by using the Box plot and the range [-3,3] of z-scores corresponding to the each variable. As a result of the controls, it was observed that there were no outliers in the data. Appropriate statistical test was determined according to whether other assumptions were met or not.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676559

RESULTS

In the first step of statistical analysis, descriptive statistics were obtained for qualitative and quantitative variables and the results are given in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. According to the results of table 2, there was a statistically significant difference in HDL scores between CSF and normal flow with CSF scores ($M = 41.50$) lower than control ($M = 47.00$) group ($U = 2649.50, p = 0.034$). Also, there was a statistically significant difference in PDW scores between CSF and control groups with CSF scores ($\bar{x} = 48.03$) higher than control ($\bar{x} = 16.06$) group ($t = 37.894, p < 0.001$). However, there is no statistically significant difference in hemogram scores between CSF and control groups ($t = 0.617, p = 0.538$).

Table 1. The descriptive statistics of qualitative variables

		Group			
		Coronary Slow Flow		Coronary Normal Flow	
		Value	Percentage (%)	Value	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	62	68.9	29	39.7
	Female	28	31.1	44	60.3
Clinic	Usap	30	33.3	0	.0
	Non-STEMI	14	15.6	2	2.7
	STEMI	5	5.6	0	.0
	Stable Angina Pectoris	29	32.2	71	97.3
	Heart Failure	8	8.9	0	.0
	Arthmia	4	4.4	0	.0
	Hypertension	Yes	40	44.4	38
	No	50	55.6	35	47.9
Diabetes mellitus	Yes	16	17.8	0	.0
	No	74	82.2	72	100.0
Hyperlipidemia	Yes	81	90.0	9	12.3
	No	9	10.0	64	87.7
Cigarette	Yes	42	46.7	12	16.4
	No	48	53.3	61	83.6
Alcohol	Yes	10	11.1	2	2.7
	No	80	88.9	71	97.3
Responsible artery	LAD	37	41.1	0	.0
	LCx	2	2.2	0	.0
	RCA	12	13.3	0	.0
	LAD- LCx	17	18.9	0	.0
	LCx -RCA	1	1.1	0	.0
	LAD-RCA	3	3.3	0	.0
	LAD-LCx-RCA	18	20.0	0	.0
	No	0	.0	73	100.0

Abbreviations:USAP: unstabil anjina pectoris, Non-STEMI:Non- st segment elevation myocardial infarction, STEMI: ST segment elevation myocardial infarction,LAD:Left anterior descending, LCx: Left Circumflex, RCA: Right coronary artery

Table 2. The comparison results of each variable across to the flow groups

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676559

	Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE	Test Statistic	p
Age (year)	CSF	90	56.1	55.00	12.10	1.28	-0.737	0.462
	Control	73	57.4	58.00	10.00	1.17		
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)	CSF	90	189.28	189.50	41.56	4.38	-0.214	0.831
	Control	73	190.64	196.00	39.26	4.59		
LDL (mg/dL)	CSF	90	108.54	105.50	33.59	3.54	-1.001	0.318
	Control	73	113.92	118.00	34.67	4.06		
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	CSF	90	14.24	14.30	1.79	0.19	0.617	0.538
	Control	73	14.08	13.90	1.55	0.18		
Lymphocyte (10 ³ /L)	CSF	90	2.19	2.10	0.79	0.08	-1.555	0.122
	Control	73	2.37	2.25	0.71	0.08		
PDW (%)	CSF	90	48.03	47.00	7.99	0.84	37.894	<0.001
	Control	73	16.06	16.10	0.40	0.05		
LCX-TFC	CSF	90	24.22	24.00	8.13	0.86	1.689	0.094
	Control	73	22.62	22.00	3.51	0.41		
Hdl (mg/dL)	CSF	90	44.59	41.50	15.18	1.60	2649.50	0.034
	Control	73	47.44	47.00	10.50	1.23		
Triglyceride (mg/dL)	CSF	90	184.22	132.50	155.26	16.37	2.12	0.036
	Control	73	145.95	132.00	64.52	7.55		
Hba1c (mmol/mol)	CSF	90	6.02	5.80	1.19	0.13	1776.50	<0.001
	Control	73	5.28	5.20	0.63	0.07		
Tsh (mIU / L)	CSF	90	2.72	1.90	6.22	0.66	3280.50	0.988
	Control	73	1.98	1.71	1.31	0.15		
Ft3 (mIU / L)	CSF	90	2.97	3.00	0.58	0.06	1688	<0.001
	Control	73	2.32	2.41	0.87	0.10		
Ft4 (mIU / L)	CSF	90	1.33	1.20	0.57	0.06	3086	0.505
	Control	73	1.20	1.18	0.28	0.03		
Hematocrit (%)	CSF	90	42.60	43.65	6.28	0.66	2963	0.282
	Control	73	41.39	42.20	6.79	0.80		
Platelet (K/uL)	CSF	90	227.78	229.00	76.35	8.05	2490	0.008
	Control	73	250.86	246.00	58.03	6.79		
Rdw (%)	CSF	90	13.92	14.00	1.92	0.20	2.71	0.008
	Control	73	13.14	13.30	1.76	0.21		
LAD-TFC	CSF	90	39.58	38.00	11.57	1.22	2066.50	<0.001
	Control	73	34.95	35.00	1.46	0.17		
RCA-TFC	CSF	90	21.26	21.00	2.91	0.34	2289	0.001
	Control	73	17.27	15.00	7.30	0.77		
LVEF	CSF	90	57.50	60.00	10.60	1.12	2461	0.004
	Control	73	58.60	60.00	2.52	0.295		
Glucose (mg/dL)	CSF	90	118.78	105.00	42.25	4.45	2509	0.010
	Control	73	101.85	99.00	14.68	1.72		
Leukocyte (µl/ml)	CSF	90	8.31	8.18	2.45	0.26	3279	0.984
	Control	73	8.15	8.20	1.77	0.21		
Leucoglycemic index	CSF	90	1.01	0.88	0.56	0.06	2.84	0.005
	Control	73	0.82	0.79	0.24	0.03		

Abbreviations: LDL: low-density lipoprotein, PDW: Platelet Distribution Width, LCx- TFC: Left Circumflex-TIMI frame count, HDL:High- density lipoprotein, Hba1c: glycated hemoglobin, TSH: thyroid stimulating hormone,Ft3: free t3, Ft4: free t4, RDW: Red Cell Distribution Width, LAD: Left anterior descending, RCA; Right coronary artery, LVEF: Left ventricular ejection fraction

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676559

The correlation results was presented in Table 3. Based on these results, it can be said that LAD TFC scores has statistically significant and positive correlation with LCX TFC score for CSF group ($r = 0.551; p = 0.0001$). Similarly, there was positive and significant correlation between RCA TFC and LCX TFC scores ($r = 0.246, p = 0.020$). These two values tend to increase or decrease together.

Table 3. The correlation analysis results between disease group. LGI and TIMI values

Group			Ladtimi	Lcxtimi	Rcatimi	LGI	
CSF	LAD-TFC	Value		0.551	-0.013	-0.004	
		p		0.0001	0.902	0.973	
	LCX-TFC	Value	0.551		0.246	0.121	
		p	0.0001		0.020	0.256	
	RCA-TFC	Value	-0.013	0.246		-0.084	
		p	0.902	0.020		0.434	
	LGI	Value	-0.004	0.121	-0.084		
		p	0.973	0.256	.434		
	Control	LAD-TFC	Value		0.020	-0.085	0.162
			p		0.865	0.475	0.170
LCX-TFC		Value	0.020		-0.004	0.144	
		p	0.865		0.975	0.223	
RCA-TFC		Value	-0.085	-0.004		0.387	
		p	0.475	0.975		0.001	
LGI		Value	0.162	0.144	0.387**		
		p	0.170	0.223	0.001		
All		LAD-TFC	Value		0.522	-0.099	0.056
			p		<0.001	0.209	0.481
	LCX-TFC	Value	0.522		0.162	0.146	
		p	<0.001		0.039	0.064	
	RCA-TFC	Value	-0.099	0.162		-0.092	
		p	0.209	0.039		0.244	
	LGI	Value	0.056	0.146	-0.092		
		p	0.481	0.064	0.244		

Abbreviations: LAD: Left anterior descending, RCA; Right coronary artery, LCx: Left Circumflex, TFC: TIMI frame count, LGI: leuko-glycemic index.

Only the variables which were found as significant in statistical tests were considered in logistic model. Table 4 provides the summary results including the coefficients, odds ratios and significance values. The confusion matrix and performance criteria based on this matrix were presented in Table 5 and 6, respectively. To observe the performance as visually, the roc curve was given in Figure 1. What stands out in all of these results, the overall logistic regression model was statistically significant ($\chi^2_{11} = 81.3, p < 0.001$). The model explained 52.6% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in CSF group and correctly classified approximately 80% of cases. The sensitivity value was calculated as 82.2%, specificity was 76.7% and area under roc curve was 86.9% (AUC: 0.869). Besides, it can be seen from the results in Table 4 that LGI, ft3, platelet, RDW,

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676559

LVEF, triglyceride, the usage of cigarette and wall movement disorder situation were found as statistically significant factor on diagnosing the CSF and control groups. The rest of variables were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). When the odds ratios were observed, higher LGI scores was associated with an increased likelihood of exhibiting CSF. LGI score is an effective factor on determination of the existence of CSF with a high odds ratio ($odds = 4.22; [1.14,15.62]$ CI 95%).

Table 4A. The significance and performance results of binomial logistic regression model

	β	SE	Z	p	Odds	CI (95%)		Model Fit Measures				
						Lower	Upper	χ^2	df	p	$R^2_{Nagelkerke}$	
Intercept	-13,92	3,51	-3,97	<,001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001					
LGI	1,44	0,67	2,15	0,03	4,22	1,14	15,62					
Ft3 (mIU / L)	1,28	0,35	3,69	<,001	3,58	1,82	7,06					
Platelet (K/uL)	-0,01	<0.001	-2,56	0,01	0,99	0,99	1,00					
Rdw (%)	0,33	0,11	2,87	0,00	1,39	1,11	1,73					
LVEF (%)	0,08	0,04	2,26	0,02	1,08	1,01	1,16	81.3	11	<0.001		0.526
Triglyceride (mg/dL)	0,01	<0.001	2,15	0,03	1,01	1,00	1,01					
Hdl (mg/dL)	0,02	0,02	0,88	0,38	1,02	0,98	1,05					
Hypertension (Yes)	-0,19	0,43	-0,44	0,66	0,83	0,36	1,92					
Cigarette (Yes)	1,18	0,54	2,19	0,03	3,27	1,13	9,44					
Alcohol (Yes)	0,56	1,09	0,52	0,60	1,76	0,21	14,81					

Table 4B. Performance metrics based on the confusion matrix

Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	AUC
0.798	0.767	0.822	0.869

ROC Curve

Abbreviations: LGI: leuko-glycemic index, Ft3: free t3, RDW: Red Cell Distribution Width, LVEF: Left ventricular ejection fraction, HDL:High- density lipoprotein.

DISCUSSION

In our study, we investigated the relationship between LGI and CSF for the first time. The most important results this study as follows, LGI was significantly higher in the CSF group than control group. According to multivariate regression analysis, LGI as a predictive marker for CSF with %86.9 accuracy.

Previous studies showed the prevalence of CSF almost 1% in acute coronary syndrome, 7% in patients who underwent elective CAG, and 4% in patients who underwent CAG for unstable angina pectoris¹⁴. In our study, the rate of CSF was 6%. Considering these rates, there is a need for non-invasive tests with high sensitivity and specificity to predict CSF. Because it will allow early diagnosis and treatment. Insulin resistance, hyperglycemia and inflammation are the main factors that play a role in the pathogenesis of CSF³. Therefore, we thought that LGI, which can evaluate both inflammation and glycemia simultaneously, can predict CSF and can be used in non-invasive evaluation.

LGI was first described by Quiroga Castro et al¹⁵. They evaluated the prognosis in patients with a diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction (AMI). They found a significant association with poor prognosis as the LGI value increased. In addition, many other studies have been published investigating its association with in-hospital mortality in AMI. Caldas et al. and Garcia Alvarez et al. also conducted studies investigating the relationship between LGI and mortality in ischemic stroke^{16,17}. Our study shows that the LGI value is a strong marker for CSF estimation.

CSF is defined as a microvascular disorder characterized by slow progression of the opaque material administered during CAG to the distal vascular structures, without obstruction in the epicardial coronary arteries¹. Loss of morphology and histopathological findings of small vessel disease such as pycnosis are shown. However, the components affecting the microvascular structure have not been fully elucidated¹⁸. Hyperglycemia, insulin resistance and inflammation are thought to be effective¹⁻⁴. We also demonstrated the independent correlation of leuko-glycemia with the presence of CSF.

There was also a positive correlation between LAD TFC, LCX TFC and RCA TFC and LGI. Higher TFC values shows more slow coronary flow. Therefore, we may say that as the LGI values related with the severity of slow flow.

In our study, while there were 60.3% men in the control group, it was observed that it was 68.9% in the CSF group. In addition, 90% of the patients in the CSF group were diagnosed with hyperlipidemia. However, our results are similar to the literature.

There are some limitations. First, it is a retrospective, cross-sectional and single-center study. Considering the number of patients and their data, the results cannot be generalized. Second, due to the limited literature on this subject, it is necessary to undertake further research. So we need further and larger studies. Finally, the study design does not give us prognostic knowledge.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676559

CONCLUSION

A high LGI was a predictor of CSF patients and was found to correlate with the TFC. The use of this simple and inexpensive index, together with other non-invasive tests before CAG, may provide some knowledge about the CSF. Prospective studies are needed to clarify the LGI and CAD severity prognostic relationship in terms of future cardiovascular events.

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676559

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